

Antidermatophytic studies of some 2-chloro-quinoline analogues

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Abstract : In this study, a series of 2-chloro-quinoline-3-carbaldehydes (**1a-g**) and (2-chloro-quinolin-3-yl)-methanols (**2a-g**) were tested for their antidermatophytic studies against four species of dermatophytes : *T. rubrum*, *E. floccosum*, *T. mentagrophytes* and *M. gypseum* by well diffusion method. Compounds **1c**, **1e** and **2a** showed good activity where as compound **2d** exhibit moderate activity when compared with that of standard fluconazole.

Keywords : 2-Chloro-3-formyl-quinoline, (2-chloro-quinolin-3-yl)-methanol, antidermatophytic activity.

Introduction

From the past decades the infections caused by dermatophytic have increased considerably. For this dermatophytic will cause pathogenic disorders in human but control measures for disorders are available with less effectiveness. Dermatophytoses cause more health issue in public concerns that too majorly for children's. The effective treatment is usually costly. There are some alternative approaches are available to control dermatophytic pathogens. So most of the researchers focused to develop new antibiotics towards industrial applications for avoid these types of infections^{1,2}. The antifungal creams which was used for treatment was mostly higher cost because of imported from other nations.

Continuation of our interest to synthesis *N*-heterocyclic compounds and their biological studies³, a number of 2-chloro-quinoline analogues have subjected for their bioactivities. In this investigation, we assessed antidermatophytic ability of 2-chloro-quinoline analogues against series of fungal pathogens which cause skin infections.

Experimental

Chemistry :

The libraries of 2-chloroquinoline derivatives such as 2-chloro-quinoline-3-carbaldehydes (**1a-g**) (Table 1)⁴ and (2-chloro-quinolin-3-yl)-methanols (**2a-g**)⁵ were selected. The reactions of acetanilide with Vilsmeier reagent gave 2-chloro-quinoline-3-carbaldehydes (**1a-g**), which upon treatment with sodiumborohydride and methanol at room temperature gave 2-chloro-quinoline-3-methanols (**2a-g**).

Table 1. Library of 2-chloro-quinoline analogues

Compd. (1a-f)/(2a-f)	Chemical Structure		R''
	(1)	(2)	
a	H	H	H
b	CH ₃	H	H
c	H	CH ₃	H
d	H	H	CH ₃
e	OCH ₃	H	H
f	H	H	OCH ₃
g	CH ₃	CH ₃	H

In vitro antidermatophytic screening :

Isolation of dermatophytes :

Four dermatophytes namely *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* [MTCC 7687], *Epidermophyton floccosum* [MTCC 7880], *Microsporium gypseum* [MTCC 2819] and *Trichophyton rubrum* [MTCC 3272] were purchased from Microbial Type Culture Collection (MTCC) as lyophilized cultures. The cultures were maintained on Sabouraud Dextrose Agar plates, incubated at 28 °C for 6 days. Further it was subjected by microscopic examination of lactophenol cotton blue mounts from the colonies.

Preliminary screening :

The quinoline analogues **1(a-g)**/**2(a-g)** were screened for antidermatophytic activity against four dermatophytes namely *T. mentagrophytes*, *E. floccosum*, *M. gypseum* and *T. rubrum* at random concentration using the well diffusion method⁶.

Different concentrations of the potentially active compounds such as **1c**, **1e**, **2a** and **2d** were screened at different concentration of 5, 10 and 15 mg in 300 μ L of DMSO and injected to wells of Sabourauds' dextrose agar plates (pH 5 and 6) was injected. Control well was made with DMSO. The test and control plates were kept for incubation at 28 °C for 96 h and everyday at a particular same time growth radius was recorded. From these records, the inhibition of zones was calculated. Fluconazole (Fig. 1) was used as a positive control. The plates were used thrice for each treatment. The potential candidates from the above mentioned experiment were found to be 15 mg dissolved in 300 μ L of DMSO (Table 2, Fig. 4).

Fig. 1. Zone of inhibition of Fluconazole and DMSO against *T. rubrum*.

Fig. 2. Zone of inhibition of compounds **1c** and **1e** against *T. rubrum*.

Results and discussion

In the present work, we have investigated the antidermatophytic capacity of the synthesized quinoline analogues (**1a-f/2a-f**) in Well diffusion method. The preliminary studies indicate that compounds **1c**, **1e**, **2a** and **2d** (Fig. 2, Fig. 3) were active against *T. rubrum*. The zone of inhibition of different concentrations of the synthesized compounds (**1c**, **1e**, **2a** and **2f**) is presented in Table 2.

Antidermatophytic activity revealed that two of the 2-chloro-quinoline-3-carbaldehyde derivatives **1c**, **1e** (Fig. 2) and one of the (2-chloro-quinolin-3-yl)-methanol derivative **2a** (Fig. 2) showed good activity where as compound **2d** (Fig. 3) exhibit moderate activity against *T. rubrum* when compared with that of standard Fluconazole. The fact is that, antidermatophytic activities of these quinoline analogues are highly interesting; the compounds such as **2a** and **2d** it shows promising activity against *T. rubrum*.

It was observed that the maximum antidermatophytic activity was shown in the tested compound **1c** having methyl group at seventh position of 2-chloro-quinoline-3-carbaldehydes system. When the aldehyde (**1c**) was reduced with sodiumborohydride it gives **2c**, which is inactive

Fig. 3. Zone of inhibition of compounds **2a** and **2d** against *T. rubrum*.

Table 2. Antidermatophytic activity of synthesized compounds

Compd.	Zone of inhibition (mm)											
	<i>T. rubrum</i>			<i>T. mentagrophytes</i>			<i>M. gypseum</i>			<i>E. floccosum</i>		
	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3
1c	-	-	40	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
1e	-	-	35	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2a	-	-	40	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2d	-	-	28	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

(1) 5 mg in 300 μ L of DMSO, (2) 10 mg in 300 μ L of DMSO, (3) 15 mg in 300 μ L of DMSO. Control - DMSO (0 mm), S - Fluconazole (35 mm).

against all organisms. The same analysis was done in compound **1a** (inactive) but we observed that compound **2a** was superior to that of standard Fluconazole. Similar result was found in **2e** also (Fig. 4).

Antidermatophytic activity against *T.rubrum*

Fig. 4. *In vitro* antidermatophytic activity against *T. rubrum*.

Conclusions

The obtained results from the above research were supported that quinoline analogues will act as a best fac-

tor in huge area applications. Thus, we concluded that three compounds (**1c**, **1e** and **2a**) were superior to positive controls against *T. rubrum* microbial strains so it can be act as the antifungal agent for dermatophytic infection.

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